

A Few 2-Methylquinazolin-4(3H)-ones as Antimicrobial Agents

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Quinazolin-4(3H)-ones possess various biological activities¹. We reported earlier the antimicrobial activities of the Schiff bases of 3-amino-2-methylquinazolin-4(3H)-ones². As functional groups like OH, NO₂, SO₃H and COOH when attached to aromatic rings are reported to impart antimicrobial activity, we planned to synthesise new title compounds in the usual way from benzoxazin-4-ones and evaluate their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

- 3a-i ; X = H
4a-i ; X = Br
Ar
3a, 4a ; *o*-C₆H₄CO₂H
3b, 4b ; *p*-C₆H₄CO₂H
3c, 4c ; *o*-C₆H₄OH
3d, 4d ; *p*-C₆H₄SO₃H
3e, 4e ; NH-2,3-(NO₂)₂C₆H₃
3f, 4f ; *p*-C₆H₄NO₂
3g, 4g ; C₆H₃-2-OH-3-CO₂H
3h, 4h ; *m*-C₆H₄OH
3i, 4i ; 2-Me-4(3H)-quinazolinone

Results and Discussion

Compounds 3h, i and 4b, f were found to be active against *Bacillus subtilis*, and 3d and 4d active against *Salmonella typhi* and *Shigella dysenteriae*. However, rest of the compounds did not show appreciable

antibacterial effects.

So far as the antifungal activity is concerned, compounds 3f, g, i and 4a, d, e, i were found to be active against *Alternaria alternata*. 3d, g, 4f, g were active against *Acremonium spp.*, and 3d and 4d resisted the growth of *Trychophyton mentogrophytes*. Only 4i was found effective against *Candida albicans*.

The study reveals that the bromination imparted antifungal activities in compounds 4a, c, e, f, h in comparison to 3a, c, e, f, h

Experimental

The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G using ethanol-chloroform-hexane (25 : 65 : 10). M.ps. were determined in open capillaries using a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 470 spectrophotometer. All the compounds showed characteristic ir bands at 1 670–1 640 (N–C=O), 1 600–1 580 (C–N) and 1 520–1 500 cm⁻¹(C=C).

2-Methyl-3-(substituted)quinazolin-4(3H)-ones (3a-i) and 2-methyl-3-(substituted)-6,8-dibromoquinazolin-4(3H)-ones (4a-i) : A mixture of anthranilic acid (1)/3, 5-dibromo anthranilic acid³ (0.05 mol) and acetic anhydride (0.1 mol) was refluxed under anhydrous conditions for 4 h. The excess of acetic anhydride was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. The intermediate benzoxazin-4-one so obtained as a solid mass was used up immediately for the next step.

A mixture of benzoxazin-4-one (0.05 mol) and primary amines (0.05 mol) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid for 4 h. It was then allowed to cool and poured in ice-cold water with stirring and was kept in a refrigerator overnight. The resulting solid was washed with distilled water, dried and crystallised from ethanol

All the compounds gave satisfactory results for nitrogen analysis report. The yield and m.p. of the compounds are as follows: **3a** (Ar = *o*-C₆H₄(COOH)), m.p. 189–90; **b** (= *p*-C₆H₄(COOH)), 56%, 184–86°; **c** (= *o*-C₆H₄(OH)), 56%, 150–51°; **d** (= *p*-C₆H₄(SO₃H)), 75%, 177–78°; **e** (= –NH-2,3-(NO₂)₂C₆H₃), 68%, 140–41°; **f** (= *p*-C₆H₄(NO₂)), 62%, 112–13°; **g** (= C₆H₃-2(OH), 3(COOH)), 54%, 107–08°; **h** (= *m*-C₆H₄(OH)), 50%, 109–11°; **i** (= 2(CH₃) 4(3H)-quinazolinone), 58%, 155–56°; **4a** (= *o*-C₆H₄(COOH)), 54%, 161–62°; **b** (= *p*-C₆H₄(COOH)), 58%, 174–75°; **c** (= *o*-C₆H₄(OH)), 52%, 139–41°; **d** (= *p*-C₆H₄(SO₃H)), 63%, 197–98°; **e** (= NH-2,3-(NO₂)₂-C₆H₄), 68%, 159–60°; **f** (= *p*-C₆H₄(NO₂)), 66%, 172–73°; **g** (= C₆H₃ 2(OH), 3(COOH)), 49%, 151–52°; **h** (= *m*-C₆H₄(OH)), 62%, 111–12°; **i** (= 2(CH₃) 4(3H)-quinazolinone), 55%, 158–59°.

Microbiological evaluation: Filter paper agar diffusion technique⁴ was used for the evaluation. For culture and biological evaluation Hi-media bacteriological broth and bacteriological nutrient agar were used against *Bacillus subtilis* (gram +ve), *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherchia coli* and *Proteus vulgaris* (all gram –ve). For antifungal studies Sabouraud dextrose broth and dextrose agar were used against *Candida albicans*, *Acremonium spp.*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Glomerella ingulata*, *Tricophyton mentogrophytes* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*. Dimethylformamide (DMF), was used for solubilising the synthesised compounds. The concentration of the compounds taken was 100 µg ml⁻¹. For the control studies DMF was used. Norfloxacin and ketoconazole

were used as standards for bacterial and fungal studies respectively. All the experiments were run in triplicates and the average values (i.e. zone of inhibition) taken.

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